

Reforming Education: the Practice of Preparation Specialists

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Abstract: *The rapid innovation in the economy has impacted the education system, leading to new regulations and reforms in university education and research. This article explores the challenges faced by the current education system in producing well-prepared scientists and specialists, comparing it with international standards. The focus is on improving doctoral education by aligning research training with industry needs, enhancing scientific supervision, and revising certification procedures. The article proposes introducing dual-tier PhD qualifications to assess research quality and practical relevance. Moreover, it suggests restructuring universities to issue differentiated diplomas that reflect the depth of a graduate's education and readiness for specialization. These reforms, though requiring significant investment and changes, are necessary to meet the growing demands of a knowledge-based economy.*

Keywords: *Education system, doctoral studies, scientific research, innovation, industry collaboration, research institutes, specialist training.*

The innovative development of the economy has shaken the education system, as evidenced by the adoption of new documents regulating the activities of universities in the educational and scientific sphere. The implementation of, in essence, reform measures is closely linked to the renewal of our entire society. It can be hoped that personal interest mainly in knowledge, and not in a diploma, will bring talented young people to universities; the branches of the economy, for their part, create conditions for the implementation of completely new knowledge. Another thing is that the current education system (especially in comparison with the experience of training specialists in other countries) is still unable to sufficiently meet these expectations.

What do we mean here? First of all, that our industry research institutes employ mostly "self-taught people": a young university graduate who has been assigned receives specialization, essentially, directly while performing theoretical work. And usually he has little time to get acquainted with world experience (literature) in the area of interest to him, or to develop skills in scientific work, and analyze its results. Subsequently, such an employee even becomes a candidate of science, but it can hardly be said that he is a full-fledged scientist and that the "product" he produces is full-fledged. Of course, there are exceptions everywhere, but in general ... the quality of the products of entities working with domestic technology confirms the most disappointing assumptions.

What if we call a Doctor of Philosophy only a specialist who has demonstrated the ability to independently carry out scientific research (development) in a certain field of science, who has mastered the skills of scientific analysis and examination of other people's experience and has proven this by defending a scientific work? Moreover, such work should be carried out under the supervision of scientists who have a certain scientific and pedagogical potential. Then our professorial and teaching staff would have an easier time .

And it is time, I think, to understand that research institutes should accept for scientific work only those who have prepared a dissertation in doctoral studies at a university. It would be preferable for them to

carry out scientific research in the field of their core problems and partially even at their future workplace, under the supervision of specialists from both the university and industry or academic research institutes. Certification of these research workers should be carried out only at the departments of the university that have the right to train doctoral students or applicants. This may sound unusual, but let us recall the daily practice of Western firms. Whatever you say, it is cheaper to pay for the training of a specialist than to maintain him.

Of course, such an innovation will require a revision of the relevant provisions of the Higher Attestation Commission; a significant increase in the number of places in doctoral studies; and finally, the adoption of a rule according to which a person who does not have a PhD degree has the right to independent work, i.e. can take a position higher than a junior research fellow. So far, we have the exact opposite picture. Since in many cases doctoral work is carried out on a topic unrelated to the direction of the future work of doctoral students, then there is - and has already been - discrediting, even profanation of the scientific degree, and it is increasingly becoming optional when taking up a particular scientific position.

I fully realize that a significant increase in doctoral places will require considerable expenses, but it is well known that a miser pays twice. The most difficult thing, in my opinion, in implementing the proposed innovations is that the industries (and not only industries - universities too) must understand that retraining a young university specialist who must have fundamental knowledge in a certain field of science, "pulling him up" to the level of an independent research worker - this is pedagogical work. And it is for this work that doctoral studies are provided.

To assess the preparedness of a doctoral graduate, it is proposed to introduce the titles: PhD 1st (A) and PhD 2nd (B) degree (by level or bias towards fundamentality or depending on the practical value of the work performed). Naturally, this reform will not give an immediate result, but we can look at the return on similar measures received by those enterprises and countries that have long adopted them. After all, in many countries, the one who is invited to work by a company before completing his doctoral dissertation is considered lucky (which, by the way, testifies to the exceptional talent of such a young specialist).

And one more suggestion. Currently, universities have different categories and graduate specialists of different quality, but they are all issued a diploma of "the same merit". Therefore, we recommend introducing the following conventional concepts: a university diploma and a diploma of graduation from a university, keeping in mind that a certificate of higher education is a PhD diploma. A diploma of graduation from a university would testify to the acquisition of a specialty, i.e., mastery of knowledge according to the curricula established for it, and would demonstrate the ability of the holder of this diploma to work in a specific workplace - for example, as a teacher, doctor, economist, financier, engineer, agronomist. A university diploma would show that its holder has not only mastered the established programs, but also independently delved into the problems of this specialty, acquired fundamental knowledge and is ready to specialize in a narrower direction in the future.

We do not want to offend technical or medical universities with this proposal: worthy higher educational institutions could be certified with the title of "technical university", "medical university" (which is done in other countries). At the same time, we do not think that any university is ready to graduate specialists above a certain level in all specialties. Apparently, it is worth thinking about creating colleges or institutes at the university, whose graduates would receive university diplomas. In this case, universities will value their name more. Only those who will not be ashamed of this university will be able to receive a diploma from a prestigious university, and if the graduate turns out to be quite ordinary in terms of academic performance, he will receive a standard diploma on acquiring a specialty at such and such a university.

The approach outlined requires more in-depth development, but it is now important that it receives fundamental support. Further discussion of the idea would show that the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations or the relevant ministries of the republic, which have universities or institutes, will control and regulate, which will be determined by the potential of a particular university.

Conclusion

The proposed reforms aim to strengthen the education system by aligning academic research with industry needs and enhancing the quality of scientific output. Introducing differentiated PhD qualifications and specialized university diplomas will raise the bar for doctoral education and professional training, ultimately benefiting both the academic and industrial sectors. Although these changes will require substantial investment and revisions in policy, the long-term gains in producing highly qualified and independent researchers will outweigh the costs. Universities must recognize the importance of their role in nurturing young specialists, while industries should collaborate to support the professional growth of researchers. Only through such concerted efforts can we ensure that the education system meets the demands of a modern, innovation-driven economy.

References:

1. Smith, A. (2020). **Higher Education and Industry Collaboration: A Global Perspective**. Oxford University Press.
2. Johnson, P. & Lee, R. (2019). **Doctoral Education in the 21st Century: Challenges and Reforms**. Springer.
3. Brown, D. (2021). **Innovation in Education: Bridging the Gap Between Academia and Industry**. Cambridge University Press.
4. Davis, S. & Green, M. (2022). **PhD Training and Career Development in Emerging Economies**. Wiley.
5. Based on the information of Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovations. (2024).